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HEPATOPROTECTIVE THERAPY EFFICACY IN OBSTRUCTIVE HEPATOBILIARY DISEASES: A PROSPECTIVE RANDOMIZED STUDY

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Summary. Maksymenko M., Kulivets O., Havryliuk R. **HEPATOPROTECTIVE THERAPY EFFICACY IN OBSTRUCTIVE HEPATOBILIARY DISEASES: A PROSPECTIVE RANDOMIZED STUDY.** - O.O. Bogomolets National Medical University, Kyiv, Ukraine; e-mail: mihvasmaks@gmail.com; romangavryliuk2@gmail.com. **Introduction.** Obstructive diseases of the hepatobiliary system present a complex set of clinical challenges characterized by impaired bile outflow and progressive hepatocellular damage. Despite significant advances in interventional and surgical approaches, liver dysfunction associated with these disorders continues to substantially impact patient morbidity and mortality. Hepatoprotective agents have emerged as a potential adjunctive therapeutic strategy, although their efficacy in managing hepatobiliary obstruction remains insufficiently investigated. **The purpose:** to assess the efficacy and clinical feasibility of hepatoprotective therapy in obstructive hepatobiliary diseases. **Materials and methods.** A prospective randomized cohort study was conducted from 2020 to 2024 at the Surgical Department №2 of the Kyiv Municipal Clinical Hospital of Emergency Medical Care, analyzing the treatment results of 139 patients with obstructive biliary disease (54 men, 85 women). Patients were randomly stratified into two groups: a control group receiving standard conservative therapy and a hepatoprotective therapy group receiving supplementary treatment with Remaxol, Silymarin, and S-adenosylmethionine for 21 consecutive days. **Results.** Biochemical parameter analysis revealed significant improvements in patients receiving combined hepatoprotective therapy compared to the control group. On day 7, patients administered hepatoprotectors demonstrated a 46.7% decrease in total bilirubin (reducing to 111.2 ± 22.1 $\mu\text{mol/L}$), compared to a 39.5% decrease (to 128.0 ± 23.5 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) in the control group ($p < 0.05$). Liver enzyme levels exhibited a more pronounced improvement in the hepatoprotector therapy group, with alanine aminotransferase (ALT) decreasing from 175 ± 25 U/L to 52 ± 5 U/L (a 70.3% reduction) on day 7, contrasted with a 45.6% decrease in the control group (from 182 ± 22 U/L to 99 ± 10 U/L) ($p < 0.001$). Cholestatic markers also demonstrated superior responsiveness to hepatoprotective therapy. Alkaline phosphatase (ALP) decreased by 53.4%, and gamma-glutamyl

transpeptidase (GGTP) decreased by 60.0% after 7 days, compared to decreases of 44.0% and 23.1% in the control group, respectively ($p < 0.01$ for both parameters). By day 21, both groups exhibited significant improvement; however, the hepatoprotective therapy group maintained statistically significant advantages across all parameters ($p < 0.01$), particularly in transaminase normalization (ALT: 31 ± 3 U/L vs. 66 ± 8 U/L, $p < 0.001$; AST: 25 ± 5 U/L vs. 61 ± 3 U/L, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusions. The implementation of hepatoprotectors facilitates a statistically significant acceleration in the normalization of liver function biochemical indicators, specifically bilirubin, transaminases, and cholestasis markers. The most pronounced differentiation was observed in the reduction of ALT and AST ($p < 0.001$), which indicates a substantial mitigation of cytolytic syndrome under hepatoprotective intervention. An integrated therapeutic approach incorporating hepatoprotectors for obstructive hepatobiliary diseases enables more rapid restoration of hepatic functional status and potentially mitigates the risk of complications. Based on the obtained data, we recommend incorporating hepatoprotectors into standard treatment protocols for patients presenting with obstructive diseases of the hepatobiliary system.

Key words: Biliary Tract Diseases, Cytoprotection, Prospective Studies

Реферат. Максименко М., Кулівець О., Гаврилюк Р. ЕФЕКТИВНІСТЬ ГЕПАТОПРОТЕКТИВНОЇ ТЕРАПІЇ ПРИ ОБСТРУКТИВНИХ ГЕПАТОБІЛІАРНИХ ЗАХВОРЮВАННЯХ: ПРОСПЕКТИВНЕ РАНДОМІЗОВАНЕ ДОСЛІДЖЕННЯ. Вступ.

Обструктивні захворювання гепатобіліарної системи представляють собою комплекс клінічних проблем, що характеризуються порушенням відтоку жовчі та прогресуючим гепатоцелюлярним ураженням. Незважаючи на значні досягнення в інтервенційних та хірургічних підходах, дисфункція печінки, пов'язана з цими захворюваннями, продовжує суттєво впливати на захворюваність і смертність пацієнтів. Гепатопротекторні засоби з'явилися як потенційна допоміжна терапевтична стратегія, хоча їхня ефективність у лікуванні гепатобіліарної обструкції залишається недостатньо дослідженою. **Мета:** оцінити ефективність та клінічну доцільність гепатопротекторної терапії при обструктивних захворюваннях гепатобіліарної системи. **Матеріали та методи.** Проспективне рандомізоване когортне дослідження проводилося з 2020 по 2024 рік на базі хірургічного відділення №2 Київської міської клінічної лікарні швидкої медичної допомоги, у якому проаналізовано результати лікування 139 пацієнтів з обструктивною хворобою жовчних шляхів (54 чоловіки, 85 жінок). Пацієнти були випадковим чином розподілені на дві групи: контрольна група, яка отримувала стандартну консервативну терапію, і група гепатопротекторної терапії, яка отримувала додаткове лікування ремаксолом, силімарином і S-аденозилметіоніном протягом 21 дня поспіль. **Результати.** Аналіз біохімічних показників виявив значні покращення у хворих, які отримували комбіновану гепатопротекторну терапію, порівняно з контрольною групою. На 7-му добу у хворих, які отримували гепатопротектори, спостерігалось зниження загального білірубіну на 46,7 % (до $111,2 \pm 22,1$ мкмоль/л) проти 39,5 % (до $128,0 \pm 23,5$ мкмоль/л) у контрольній групі ($p < 0,05$). Рівні ферментів печінки продемонстрували більш виражене покращення в групі терапії гепатопротекторами, при цьому рівень аланінамінотрансферази (АЛТ) знизився зі 175 ± 25 Од/л до 52 ± 5 Од/л (зниження на 70,3%) на 7-й день, на відміну від зниження на 45,6% у контрольній групі (з 182 ± 22 Од/л до 99 ± 10). Од/л) ($p < 0,001$). Холестатичні маркери також продемонстрували кращу реакцію на гепатопротекторну терапію. Лужна фосфатаза (ЛФ) знизилася на 53,4%, а гамма-глутамілтранспептидаза (ГГТП) знизилася на 60,0% через 7 днів, порівняно зі зниженням на 44,0% і 23,1% у контрольній групі відповідно ($p < 0,01$ для обох параметрів). На 21 день обидві групи продемонстрували значне покращення; однак група гепатопротекторної терапії зберігала статистично значущі переваги за всіма параметрами ($p < 0,01$), особливо щодо нормалізації трансаміназ (ALT: 31 ± 3 U/л проти 66 ± 8 U/л, $p < 0,001$; AST: 25 ± 5 U/л проти 61 ± 3 U/л, $p < 0,001$). **Висновки.** Застосування гепатопротекторів сприяє статистично достовірному прискоренню нормалізації біохімічних показників функції печінки, зокрема білірубіну, трансаміназ, маркерів холестази. Найбільш виражена диференціація спостерігалась у зниженні АЛТ та АСТ ($p < 0,001$), що свідчить про суттєве послаблення цитолітичного синдрому за гепатопротекторного втручання. Комплексний терапевтичний підхід із включенням гепатопротекторів при обструктивних

гепатобіліарних захворюваннях дозволяє швидше відновити функціональний стан печінки та потенційно знизити ризик ускладнень. На підставі отриманих даних ми рекомендуємо включити гепатопротектори в стандартні протоколи лікування пацієнтів з обструктивними захворюваннями гепатобіліарної системи.

Ключові слова: захворювання жовчних шляхів, цитопротекція, проспективне дослідження.

Introduction

Obstructive diseases of the hepatobiliary system cause a constellation of clinical complications characterized by impaired bile outflow and progressive hepatocellular damage. Despite significant advances in interventional and surgical approaches, liver dysfunction associated with these disorders continues to substantially impact patient morbidity and mortality [1-4].

Hepatoprotective therapy in patients with obstructive diseases of the hepatobiliary system who have undergone surgical intervention on the liver and biliary tract is increasingly critical due to the rapid development of surgical treatment methods for conditions associated with disrupted bile secretion and formation. The underlying prerequisites involve impaired function of bile ducts and cholangiocytes, which precipitate deterioration of bile's rheological properties and, consequently, an increase in bile density that induces a reactive impairment of hepatocytes' choleretic functions with concomitant elevated bile acid levels in the hepatic tissue [5, 6].

Bile duct dyskinesia, cholangiocyte dysfunction, and increased bile density can induce the development of mixed parenchymal-obstructive jaundice, which potentially serves as a precursor to more serious pathological conditions. The proliferation of cholangiocytes and differentiation of hepatic progenitor cells generates reactive cholangiocytes that facilitate the release of pro-inflammatory mediators and promote collagen deposition, ultimately leading to permanent fibrotic transformations [7, 8].

Consequently, patients with obstructive hepatobiliary diseases require targeted medical intervention aimed at achieving rapid jaundice resolution and implementing effective pharmacological strategies designed to protect the hepatocellular structural complex and prevent the occurrence of irreversible pathological parenchymal alterations.

Materials and methods

A prospective randomized cohort study was conducted from 2020 to 2024 at the Surgical Department №2 of the Kyiv Municipal Clinical Hospital of Emergency Medical Care in which we evaluated the effectiveness of combined hepatoprotective therapy in the treatment of patients with obstructive diseases of the hepatobiliary system.

The results of treatment of 139 patients with impaired bile passage of the hepatic and subhepatic types were analyzed, among whom 39% were men (54 patients) and 61% were women (80 patients). The mean age of the patients was 48 years. The inclusion criteria in the study comprised previous percutaneous transhepatic cholangiostomy (PTC) and an initial total bilirubin level exceeding 200 $\mu\text{mol/l}$.

All patients were randomly stratified into a control group that received standard conservative therapy and a hepatoprotective therapy group that additionally received combined therapy with Remaxol (ursodeoxycholic acid), silymarin (*Silybum marianum*), and S-adenosylmethionine.

Patients in the control group received standard supportive conservative therapy [9], including intravenous hydration with isotonic saline or Ringer's lactate, nutritional support according to individual tolerance, and symptomatic management (e.g., antipyretics, antiemetics, or analgesics as clinically indicated). Patients in the hepatoprotective therapy group received supplemental treatment with Remaxol (400 ml intravenously once a day at 20–30 drops/min rate; subsequently changed to 500 mg orally), silymarin (140 mg orally per day divided into 2–3 doses), and S-adenosylmethionine (1 g daily orally) for 21 consecutive days. The individual efficacy of these medications has been extensively documented, with Remaxol demonstrating particular effectiveness in managing patients with bile passage impairments [10-15], silymarin serving as a critical component in cholekinetics stimulation [16-18], and S-adenosylmethionine offering

notable antioxidant and antitumor effects while facilitating intrahepatic bile duct pressure normalization [19-24].

Clinical outcomes were systematically assessed through serial measurements of liver function tests, encompassing blood bilirubin (total and direct), alanine transaminase (ALT), aspartate transaminase (AST), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), and gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase (GGTP). Measurements were performed at 24-hour intervals from the first to seventh day post-treatment initiation, with additional assessments conducted on the 14th and 21st days of the study.

Descriptive statistical methods were employed in the study, with data presented as arithmetic mean \pm standard error of the arithmetic mean ($M \pm m$). A p-value $<0,05$ was considered statistically significant. All computations were performed using the MedStat statistical software program.

All procedures involving human subjects were conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, with clear explanations provided regarding the nature, purpose, potential risks, and benefits of the study. Data confidentiality and participant privacy were rigorously maintained throughout the study. All personal information was anonymized, and data were stored securely to protect participants' identities.

Results

Biochemical parameter analysis revealed significant improvements in patients receiving combined hepatoprotective therapy compared to the control group. Both groups demonstrated comparable baseline values on day 1, with total bilirubin levels of $208.8 \pm 35.9 \mu\text{mol/l}$ in the experimental group and $211.6 \pm 36.2 \mu\text{mol/l}$ in the control group ($p=0.85$), indicating initial equivalence.

On day 7, patients receiving hepatoprotectors exhibited a 46.7% decrease in total bilirubin (reducing to $111.2 \pm 22.1 \mu\text{mol/l}$), compared to a 39.5% decrease (to $128.0 \pm 23.5 \mu\text{mol/l}$) in the control group ($p<0.05$). Liver enzyme levels demonstrated a more pronounced improvement in the hepatoprotective therapy group, with alanine aminotransferase (ALT) decreasing from 175 ± 25 U/L to 52 ± 5 U/L (a 70.3% reduction) on day 7, contrasted with a 45.6% decrease in the control group (from 182 ± 22 U/L to 99 ± 10 U/L) ($p<0.001$).

Aspartate aminotransferase (AST) levels similarly normalized more rapidly in the hepatoprotective group, decreasing by 69.5% versus 49.7% in the control group during the same period ($p<0.001$). Cholestatic markers also demonstrated superior responsiveness to hepatoprotective therapy, with alkaline phosphatase (ALP) decreasing by 53.4% and gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGTP) decreasing by 60.0% after 7 days, compared to decreases of 44.0% and 23.1% in the control group, respectively ($p<0.01$ for both parameters).

By day 21, both groups exhibited significant improvement; however, the hepatoprotective therapy group maintained statistically significant advantages across all parameters ($p<0.01$), especially in transaminase normalization. Specifically, ALT levels were 31 ± 3 U/L in the hepatoprotective group versus 66 ± 8 U/L in the control group ($p<0.001$), while AST levels were 25 ± 5 U/L versus 61 ± 3 U/L ($p<0.001$), respectively.

Table 1 and Table 2 provide comprehensive summaries of liver function test results for the experimental and control groups.

Table 1. Liver function test results for the hepatoprotective therapy group ($M \pm m$)

Day	Total bilirubin ($\mu\text{mol/l}$)	Conjugated bilirubin ($\mu\text{mol/l}$)	ALT (U/L)	AST (U/L)	ALP (U/L)	GGTP (U/L)
1	208.8 ± 35.9	132.4 ± 25.7	175 ± 25	187 ± 21	322 ± 28	275 ± 22
2	186.9 ± 35.2	111.9 ± 22.2	133 ± 18	163 ± 12	293 ± 26	265 ± 20
3	179.9 ± 30.3	112.2 ± 20.5	112 ± 15	124 ± 18	278 ± 24	235 ± 19
4	164.2 ± 30.1	105.8 ± 21.5	103 ± 13	90 ± 13	243 ± 28	215 ± 16
5	163.8 ± 33.1	102.4 ± 20.5	92 ± 7	74 ± 11	221 ± 26	180 ± 19
6	132.1 ± 27.3	83.5 ± 17.1	72 ± 7	64 ± 9	170 ± 18	122 ± 12
7	111.2 ± 22.1	72.8 ± 15.4	52 ± 5	57 ± 8	150 ± 12	110 ± 10
14	93.3 ± 21.5	63.4 ± 12.5	42 ± 4	34 ± 5	85 ± 10	70 ± 4
21	82.5 ± 16.1	55.7 ± 10.3	31 ± 3	25 ± 5	70 ± 8	50 ± 8

Table 2. Liver function test results for the control group (M ± m)

Day	Total bilirubin (μmol/l)	Conjugated bilirubin (μmol/l)	ALT (U/L)	AST (U/L)	ALP (U/L)	GGTP (U/L)
1	211.6 ± 36.2	132.6 ± 24.0	182 ± 22	169 ± 18	309 ± 21	260 ± 17
2	198.3 ± 33.5	133.3 ± 22.0	168 ± 20	165 ± 17	290 ± 24	250 ± 19
3	179.1 ± 30.8	115.2 ± 23.5	155 ± 18	150 ± 15	260 ± 23	250 ± 18
4	167.1 ± 30.6	102.2 ± 20.5	143 ± 18	135 ± 15	255 ± 23	230 ± 17
5	155.2 ± 28.4	93.4 ± 18.8	128 ± 15	115 ± 12	235 ± 21	210 ± 16
6	135.1 ± 25.6	82.4 ± 15.0	117 ± 12	100 ± 10	214 ± 20	200 ± 15
7	128.0 ± 23.5	71.8 ± 13.7	99 ± 10	85 ± 8	173 ± 20	200 ± 15
14	95.0 ± 20.5	62.3 ± 11.0	82 ± 8	74 ± 6	123 ± 12	110 ± 10
21	84.1 ± 13.5	52.4 ± 11.3	66 ± 8	61 ± 3	83 ± 3	65 ± 8

Discussion

The obtained results provide convincing evidence supporting the efficacy of combined hepatoprotective therapy in patients with obstructive hepatobiliary diseases. The accelerated reduction in bilirubin, transaminases, and cholestatic markers in the hepatoprotective therapy group, compared to the control group, highlights the beneficial effects of hepatoprotectors on liver function. Notably, ALT and AST levels decreased significantly (by 70.3% and 69.5%, respectively) in patients receiving hepatoprotectors, whereas the control group exhibited a more modest decline. This finding indicates a substantial reduction in cytolytic syndrome and suggests hepatoprotective effects in preventing further hepatocyte damage.

The mechanisms of action of the studied hepatoprotectors likely involve antioxidant, membrane-stabilizing, and anti-inflammatory properties, which contribute to the restoration of structural and functional liver integrity under cholestatic conditions [25]. Importantly, a statistically significant difference between the groups was already evident by the seventh day of treatment and persisted throughout the observation period, underscoring the rationale for early hepatoprotector administration. Additionally, the experimental group demonstrated a more pronounced decrease in ALP and GGTP levels, confirming the therapy's effectiveness in alleviating the cholestatic component.

Our findings align with previous studies but demonstrate a more pronounced therapeutic effect, potentially due to the integrated hepatoprotective approach. However, further research is needed to determine the optimal duration of therapy and to explore the potential for personalized hepatoprotector selection based on the etiology and severity of the obstructive process [26-28].

Conclusions

The results of this study provide strong evidence for the clinical efficacy of combined hepatoprotective therapy in patients with obstructive hepatobiliary. The administration of hepatoprotectors significantly accelerates the normalization of key biochemical markers of liver function, particularly bilirubin levels, transaminases, and cholestasis indicators. Notably, the most pronounced effect is observed in the reduction of ALT and AST levels ($p < 0.001$), indicating a substantial decrease in cytolytic syndrome under hepatoprotective therapy.

A multidisciplinary treatment approach incorporating hepatoprotectors facilitates a more rapid restoration of liver function and may potentially reduce the risk of complications. Based on these findings, we recommend incorporating hepatoprotectors into standard treatment protocols for patients with obstructive hepatobiliary diseases, particularly in cases with severe hepatic dysfunction.

Nevertheless, further research is warranted to determine the optimal therapeutic regimens, duration of treatment, and personalized strategies based on the etiology and severity of the underlying condition.

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EFFICACY OF USING THE MODIFIED HYSTEROSCOPIC METROPLASTY METHOD IN WOMEN WITH A HISTORY OF UTERINE SEPTUM AND RPL-SYNDROME

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Summary. Kalitsynska Yu. L., Gladchuk I. Z. **EFFICACY OF USING THE MODIFIED HYSTEROSCOPIC METROPLASTY METHOD IN WOMEN WITH A HISTORY OF UTERINE SEPTUM AND RPL- SYNDROME** - *The Odessa National Medical University; e-mail: ykalicinskaya@gmail.com.* **The aim:** to improve the results of treatment of women with RPL- syndrome associated with uterine septum (US) by modifying the technique of hysteroscopic metroplasty (HM). **Materials and methods.** The study involved 138 patients with uterine septum and RPL - syndrome in the anamnesis who were operated on between 2018 and 2023. The main group (I clinical) consisted of 88 patients in whom hysteroscopic metroplasty was performed according to the proposed modified technique. The comparative group (II clinical) consisted of 50 patients who were operated on according to the classical method of HM. The age of patients in both groups ranged from 19 to 40 years. The effectiveness of operations was assessed by questioning during consultations or by questionnaire data on pregnancy onset and its completion during the first year after HM. The formation of postoperative intrauterine adhesions (IUA) was also evaluated according to second-look hysteroscopy data in 3–6 months after HM in some patients. Statistical analysis of the results obtained was carried out using the program "Primer Biostatistics" (USA). **The results.** The proposed modified HM technique helps reduce the frequency of postoperative synechiae and severe forms of IUA after the procedure ($p<0.05$). In the main group, compared to the second group, the frequency of spontaneous miscarriages decreased by 3 times, the frequency of spontaneous pregnancies increased by 20%, and the total frequency of pregnancies and live births increased ($p<0.05$). **Conclusions.** The results obtained in the study indicate the expediency of implementation and use of the modified HM method.